

Natural Potential of Soils in the North-Eastern Region of the Sofia Field for Growing Agricultural Crops

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Abstract

On the basis of up-to-date soil data for certain soil differences, land evaluation of suitability for crops was made in the areas of the villages of Gorna Malina, Grigorevo and Gorni Bogrov, Elin Pelin Municipality, Sofia District. The relative evaluation was carried out by applying the Methodology for Work on the Cadastre of Agricultural Lands in the People's Republic of Bulgaria (Petrov et al., 1988), as well as newly developed methodologies (for field ratings for barley (*Hordeum sativum* L.) and einkorn wheat (*Triticum monococcum* L.)). A brief description of the climate conditions for the region is made and the main physical and chemical characteristics of the studied soils are presented. Field ratings are calculated for some basic cereals and technical crops. The obtained values indicate, which soils have suitable conditions for development of agricultural crops and which lands are unsuitable for the crops presented.

Key words: field rating, wheat growing conditions, common barley and six-rowed barley, einkorn, corn, sunflower, linseed.

Introduction

The municipality of Gorna Malina is located in the central part of Western Bulgaria, covering the eastern part of the Sofia valley, the Saranska and Kamara valleys. The agricultural lands in the municipality are suitable for growing cereals, technical and fodder crops. Due to the relatively low temperatures during the growing season, it is not advisable to grow heat-loving crops in the area. According to the soil-geographical zoning (Poushkarov, 1913, Tanov, 1946), the studied soils were formed in the northeastern part of the Sofia field, which were studied in the lands of Botunets, Bogrov, Gorna Malina, Grigorevo, Kumaritsa, Elin Pelin, Chelophechene, etc.

In these areas, their geographical distribution is closely dependent on geomorphological forms. In this regard, the Sofia valley and the fence mountains are characterized by different geomorphological forms that form the relief of the soil cover with shallow soils. The studied areas include not high hilly hills and low-valley fields, where the

soils are developed under the direct influence of the weathering process and alternate weak shallows with deep soils.

The Sofia valley is covered by mountains with variety of plant species, both in the high and low parts of the region. The lower part has flat relief, where low and high terraces are observed. The most developed is the floodplain terrace, which is swampy in some places, especially along the valley of the Lesnovska River.

The landscape fragmentation and regionalization is multifaceted and this determines the wide distribution of deciduous and afforestation with coniferous vegetation, the abundance of grass and tree species, of which, the most common are elm (*Ulmus minor* L.), turkey oak (*Quercus cerris* L.), pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.), dog woods (*Cornus mas* L.), wild pear (*Pyrus pyraster* L.), wild plum (*Prunus spinosa* L.), dog rose (*Rosa canina* L.), hawthorn (*Crataegus* sp.), perennial grass (*Chrysopogon gryllus* L.), sheep and red fescue (*Festuca ovina* L. & *Festuca rubra* L.), white and red clover (*Trifolium repens* L. & *Trifolium pretense* L.), horsetail (*Equisetums* sp.), bulrush (*Typha* sp.), etc. This diversity, strongly influenced by the relief forms and rocks, is one of the reasons for the formation of great soil diversity. Acidic grass formations, which annually leave significant amounts of organic plant residues on the surface and in the soil, are of particular importance in the processes of humus formation and humus accumulation (Dimitrov, G., 2015).

The aim of the study is to present brief description of the soil and climate conditions in the area of the villages of Gorna Malina, Grigorevo and Gorni Bogrov, Elin Pelin Municipality, and to make relative evaluation for agricultural crops on certain soil differences in the area, recommending the most suitable soils for their cultivation.

Materials and Methods

The main indicators and parameters used in the land evaluation are the climate conditions in the area, the qualities of soils, which are determined by the soil scientist in the field (through a diagnostic description of the soil profile), physical and chemical soil properties (determined in laboratory conditions) and the requirements of agricultural crop (to soil and climate), for which the relative evaluation is made.

- ***Climate conditions***

The lands of the studied sites fall within the climate region of the high fields of Western Central Bulgaria (Sabev and Stanev, 1963).

Here, the continental character of the climate is best expressed by the relatively large annual amplitude of the seasons – warm summers and cold winters (Hershkovich, 1962). For the climate characteristic, data from the meteorological station of the town of Elin Pelin are presented.

Gorna Malina and the villages of Grigorevo and Gorni Bogrov are located at about 550 m above sea level, south of the Balkan Mountains. In winter, the average temperature for January varies from minus 2.0°C to minus 3.5°C, and the number of days with minimum temperature below minus 10°C for the three winter months is 15-20. The hollow nature of the terrain creates favorable conditions for retention and additional cooling of the air masses, which is why when cold air enters, some of the lowest minimum temperatures are obtained.

In summer, large number of days are above 25°C, and on days with intense warming, the temperature reaches 35°C, with the soil temperature being 3-4°C higher than that of the

air. In autumn, the temperature drops sharply with almost the same amplitudes with which it rises by months in the spring. (Climatic reference book for the People's Republic of Bulgaria, vol. 3., 1983).

The average long-term precipitation is 574 mm. The least precipitation falls in January – March. Winter precipitation is 103 mm (17.9% of the total annual precipitation). In April and May, the amount of precipitation increases to reach its maximum in June. Average spring precipitation is 153 mm (26.6%) and summer precipitation is 192 mm (33.4%). August is characterized by the least rainfall in summer (44 mm). In September, precipitation decreases and reaches 35 mm and since October there has been an increase in its amount. The total precipitation in autumn is 131 mm (22.8 %) (Koleva & Peneva, 1990).

According to zoning by humidification conditions, the sites fall into arid zone, where the difference between precipitation and evaporation (mm) for the period June-August is from minus 200 to minus 300 mm. According to the zoning by temperature conditions (temperature sum (°C) for the period with air temperature above 100°C), the sites fall in moderately warm to moderately cool area (1600-31000) (Hershkovich, 1984).

- **Brief description of crop requirements for soil and climate conditions**

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), **barley** (*Hordeum sativum* L. ssp. *vulgare* & spp. *distichum*) and **corn** (*Zea mays* L.). For these crops, medium to heavy sandy-clayey soils (physical clay content 45-60%), thick humus horizon and neutral to slightly alkaline reaction (pH in water 6.5-7.5) are most suitable. To assess the climate conditions in autumn crops, a "deficit in the moisture balance for the period April-June" is applied, with winter stock included. In the case of maize, climatic conditions are assessed by "deficit in the moisture balance for the period June-August" and the sum of temperatures above 100C in connection with the cultivation of early, mid-early or late varieties.

Einkorn and emmer (*Triticum monococcum* L. & *Triticum dicoccum* Schübl.) - in terms of soil requirements, both types of einkorn are unpretentious. They can grow on poor, impermeable, stony and low-fertile soils. For optimal development of the crop, the soils should have mechanical composition of medium to heavy sandy loam (physical clay content 45-60%), with thick (over 40 cm.) and rich in organic matter (over 2%) humus-accumulative horizon, neutral to slightly alkaline soil reaction (pH in H₂O 6.5 - 7.5), low groundwater level (100-200 cm from the soil surface), loose structure and good physical and water properties. To assess the climate conditions of einkorn, a "deficit in the moisture balance for the period April-June" is applied, including winter stock.

Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) is not one of the crops particularly demanding on soil conditions. The plant has strong and deep root system, so it is best to grow on soils with deep profile. Soils shallower than 30 cm are unsuitable for growing sunflower. The crop receives optimal development on soils with heavy sandy-loamy to slightly clayey mechanical composition (physical clay content 45 to 75%). Very light soils (sandy and clay-sandy) have poor water retention capacity, low capillary rise and under the precipitation conditions, typical for our country, are not suitable for growing sunflower without irrigation. The optimal soil reaction (pH) for sunflower is from 5 to 7.5. The more acidic reaction (below 5) leads to bad effect on yields and can reduce them to 50 % or more, even to completely fail them. When assessing climate conditions, the indicator "deficit in the balance of moisture and average

temperatures for the period June-July" is applied, taking into account the winter stock of soils (Koedzhikov et al., 1971).

Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) is grown for fiber and for oil. When the crop is grown for fiber, it is used in the textile industry, and when grown for oil, it is used in the production of varnishes, birch, etc. It is a spring crop that is sown for the region of Southern Bulgaria at the beginning of March, and for the mountainous regions at the end of April. The optimum temperature for seed germination in flax is 8-10°C. Due to its weak root system, flax requires, first of all, soils rich in available nutrients. The soils should be aerated, medium sandy-loamy. On heavy and very waterlogged soils, plants suffer from fungal diseases. Acidic soils are not suitable for this culture. When assessing climatic conditions, a moisture coefficient and an average humidity deficit for the germination-flowering period are applied (Koedzhikov et al., 1971).

- **Soil differences**

The report presents 10 soil profiles. Eight of them are located on the territory of the village of Gorna Malina, one in the village of Grigorevo and one in the village of Gorni Bogrov. The main soil indicators that are included in the calculation of the field ratings are presented in table 1. Location of the soil profiles is shown on figure 1. The soils for which the relative evaluation has been made are presented below, including information on location, altitude, slope and soil-forming rock.

Figure 1. Soil profile locations (Source: Google Earth, 2024)

Profile 1. Primitive soils – Lithosoils (*Ferric lithosoils*), *Haplic Leptosol* (*Eutric, Skeletic*) (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2006). Location of the profile is on altitude of 660 m in the land of the village of Gorna Malina, Sofia region, in the lower part of a ridge (saddle) with 20° slope to the north. Soil-forming rock is sandstone (Dimitrov, 2015).

Profile 2. Medium leached cinnamon forest soils, *Cutanic Luvisol (Siltic, Rhodic)* (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2006). The profile is located on altitude of 629 m in the land of the village of Gorna Malina, in the lower part of a slope with slope of 15° to the east. Soil-forming materials are sandy loam, carbonate deposits (deluvium) (Dimitrov, 2015).

Profile 3. Dark rankers, *Haplic Leptosol (Humic, Eutric, Skeletic)* (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2006). Location of the profile is on altitude of 620 m in the land of the village of Gorna Malina. The relief of the area is hilly. The profile is set in the upper part of a slope with 20° slope. The soil-forming rock is iron-bearing quartzites (Dimitrov, 2015).

Profile 4. Ferric rankers. *Haplic Leptosol (Humic, Eutric, Skeletic)* (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2006). The profile is located on altitude of 598 m in the land of the village of Gorna Malina, in the upper part of the ridge with a slope of 6°. The soil-forming rock is granitogneiss and quartzites (Dimitrov, 2015).

Profile 5. Highly leached cinnamon forest soils, *Haplic Luvisol (Siltic, Rhodic)* (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2006). Location of the profile is on altitude of 620 m in the land of the village of Gorna Malina, in the lower part of a slope with 6° slope to the southeast. Soil-forming materials are sandy-loamy (deluvial) deposits (Dimitrov, 2015).

Profile 6. Heavily leached cinnamon forest soils, *Haplic Luvisol (Siltic, Rhodic, Skeletic)* (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2006). The profile is located on altitude of 662 m in the land of the village of Gorna Malina, in the lower part of a slope with 5° slope to the north. The soil-forming rock is semi-weathered red sandstone (Dimitrov, 2015).

Profile 7. Ferric rankers, *Haplic Leptosol (Humic, Eutric, Skeletic)* (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2006). Location of the profile is on altitude of 652 m in the land of the village of Gorna Malina. The relief of the area is dissected hilly. The soil profile is set in the upper part of a slope with 5° slope to the north. Soil-forming rock is semi-weathered sandstone (Dimitrov, 2015).

Profile 8. Typical cinnamon forest soils, *Haplic Cambisol (Manganiferic, Eutric, Clayic, Rhodic)* (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2006). The profile is located on altitude of 630 m in the land of the village of Gorna Malina. The relief of the area is hilly. The soil profile is set in the lower part of a slope with 4° slope to the southeast. Soil-forming materials are Quaternary deposits (Dimitrov, 2015).

Profile 9. Chervenozem, *Haplic Luvisol (Clayic, Rhodic)* (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2006). Location of the profile is on altitude of 585 m in the land of the village of Grigorevo, Sofia region. The relief of the area is flat. Soil-forming materials are Quaternary deposits (Dimitrov, 2015).

Profile 10. Vertical (Resinous) Luvisols, *Haplic Luvisol (Clayic, Chromic)* (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2006). The profile is located on altitude of 552 m in the land of the village of Gorni Bogrov, Sofia region. The relief of the area is flat-hilly, the soil profile is set with 2° slope to the southeast. Soil-forming materials are fine Quaternary materials (Dimitrov, 2015).

Table 1. Main soil indicators for relative evaluation of agricultural lands in the objects of study (Dimitrov, 2015).

Soil Profile №	Physical clay, top layer, %	Physical clay, sub layer, %	Humus horizon thickness, cm	Soil profile thickness, cm	Texture factor.	pH H ₂ O	Humus %	Ground-water level
1- Gorna Malina	14.0	6.0	8.0	40	<1.0	6,3	3,1	deep
2 - Gorna Malina	25.0	49.5	25	90	2.9	6.5	4,3	deep
3 - Gorna Malina	16.0	16.0	24	24	1.0	5.8	4.7	deep
4 - Gorna Malina	22.0	22.0	25	25	1.0	5.1	5.9	deep
5 - Gorna Malina	35.0	48.0	25	75	2.5	5.5	2.4	deep
6 - Gorna Malina	30.0	38.0	31	83	2.1	6.1	3.5	deep
7 - Gorna Malina	15.0	15.0	20	40	<1.0	4.9	4.8	deep
8 - Gorna Malina	56.0	55.0	25	144	1.1	6.4	0.7	deep
9 - Grigorevo	52.0	66.0	30	155	1.2	5.9	2.6	deep
10- Gorni Bogrov	67.0	74.0	30	200	1.2	5.5	2.4	deep

The land evaluation for the chosen agricultural crops in the studied sites was carried out according to the Methodology for Working with the Cadastre of Agricultural Lands in the Republic of Bulgaria (Petrov et al., 1988) (for wheat, corn, sunflower, fiber flax). Evaluation of lands for fodder and malting barley is calculated using the methods for land evaluation under non-irrigated conditions (Krasteva, 2002). Soil conditions for einkorn are evaluated in accordance with Mitreva et al. (2016).

Determination of field ratings is carried out on the basis of data from the soil samples taken for analysis for physical and chemical soil properties, the relief, the soil-forming materials, the climate, as well as the biological characteristics of the individual crops.

Field ratings are grouped into 5 field classes, similar to Hristov and Mitreva (2021), according to the suitability of lands for growing main agricultural crops at 100-point system (table 2).

Table 2. Field classes and evaluation ratings

Field class	Evaluation rating
First group (very good lands)	over 91
	81-90
Second group (Good Lands)	71-80
	61-70
Third group (medium-good lands)	51-60
	41-50
Fourth group (bad lands)	31-40
	21-30
Fifth group (unsuitable lands)	11-20
	0-10

- **Field rating**

The land productivity can be presented through the relative evaluation for crops. It is comparative assessment of agricultural land based on its characteristics or qualities and shows its suitability for growing one or group of crops at a given level of agricultural technology.

Climate, precipitation, temperature, balance of atmospheric humidity, risky weather conditions, etc. are reported parameters characterizing the assessed area (Climate Guide for the People's Republic of Bulgaria, vol. 2., 1979; Climate Guide for the People's Republic of Bulgaria, vol. 3., 1983; Koleva and Peneva, 1990; Stanev et al., 1991).

Soil. To assess the soil conditions, the main characteristics of the soil and subsoil in the studied areas were used, which determine its fertility and have direct relationship with the productivity of agricultural lands.

Plant requirements. A differentiated approach has been applied, depending on the plant species, climate conditions through phenophases determining development, and soil and soil-forming conditions (Koedzhikov et al., 1971).

On the basis of presented data on soils in the northeastern part of Sofia field, their physical and chemical properties, taking into account the climate features in the region, land evaluation was made for selected agricultural crops in accordance with the "Methodology for Work on the Cadastre of Agricultural Lands" using the equation (Petrov et al., 1988, Georgiev, 2006).

$$FR_x = \frac{R_{TX} + R_{THH} + R_{TSP} + R_{CCR} + R_{pH} + R_{HC} + R_{GWT}}{n^R} k_{EA} k_{SA} k_{ST} k_{FL} k_{CL}$$

Where:

FR x -Field rating for Relevant Crops

Field ratings for:

R_{TX} – soil mechanical composition; R_{THH}- thickness of the humus horizon; R_{TSP} - thickness of the soil profile; R_{CCR}- textural profile differentiation; R_{pH}- soil reaction; R_{HC} - content of organic matter (humus); R_{GWT}- groundwater level.

Correction coefficients for:

k_{EA}- soil erosion or soil accumulation; k_{SA}- soil salinity/alkalinity;
k_{ST}- stoniness of the arable soil layer; k_{FL}-swampy; k_{CL}-climate; ^R - number of included characteristics (R ...).

The quality assessment of crops takes into account the specific requirements of the crop to soil and climate conditions. The field rating is numerical expression of suitability of environmental conditions for development of each of the crops given the specific soil difference. The field rating is the final estimate and is the sum of the ratings of each indicator presented in the equation above. The evaluation of individual indicators and the complex determination of the field rating are with values from 0 to 100, under non-irrigated conditions.

The climate conditions are assessed by indicators (deficit in the moisture balance for the period April-June; temperature sums for the period with temperatures above 10°C; hydrothermal coefficient; probability of negative temperatures in April, etc.), all of which involve air temperature and precipitation. The assessment of moisture supply is of great importance for wheat, barley, einkorn, corn, sunflower and linseed.

Results and Discussion

Field ratings by crops for the studied sites (table 3) are made according to the above equation, using the specific physico-chemical indicators for each soil. The ratings reflects erosion (through the indicated degrees of slope), as well as climate conditions. It should be noted that for wheat, barley and einkorn, the climate conditions are estimated by "deficit in moisture balance for the period April-June", which, for the area of these lands, is minus 25 mm (the climate assessment is 100). This shows that in climate terms the region is suitable for cereals.

To assess the climate conditions for corn and sunflower, the indicator "deficit in the moisture balance for the period June-August" is applied, which, for the region of the Sofia field, is minus 200 to minus 300 mm. That deficit is significant and for this reason the assessment of climate indicator for crops is 68. The climate conditions in the cultivation of fiber linseed are evaluated by the indicator "Moisture coefficient and average humidity deficit for the period of germination-flowering", which, for the area of the sites, is at 80 and indicates relatively good climatic conditions for growing this technical crop.

Table 3. Land evaluation of studied soils for the individual crops

Soil profiles	Field ratings for crops						
	wheat	barley six-rowed	barley common	einkorn	corn	sunflower	linseed
Profile 1	34	38	38	38	16	19	46
Profile 2	63	67	66	70	35	39	53
Profile 3	25	25	25	30	0	0	46
Profile 4	35	25	25	30	0	0	50
Profile 5	77	80	78	85	46	50	61
Profile 6	74	87	85	85	46	49	67
Profile 7	33	45	43	38	14	16	52
Profile 8	76	84	82	80	48	53	66
Profile 9	93	95	93	85	61	65	72
Profile 10	82	90	88	80	51	60	80

(Ferric lithosols - Profile 1); (Dark Rankers - Profile 3); (Ferric rankers - Profile 4 and 7) are soils with low-density profile, with 25 to 40 cm thickness and loose layer of rocky soil-forming materials below. They have a clay-sandy mechanical composition (10-20% physical clay) and are located on sloping terrain. This determines the low field rating for wheat (table 3) and categorized them as "bad" lands. For barley, einkorn and corn the lands are "unsuitable". These soils have highest field rating for growing linseed, which determines them as "medium good" lands.

Leached cinnamon forest soils - Profile 2, Profile 5, Profile 6; Typical cinnamon forest soils - Profile 8; Chervenozem - Profile 9; *Vertic (Resin-shaped) cinnamon forest soils* (Profile 10 Vertical (Resinous) Luvisols) have normal soil profile.

The thickness of the soil profile for the soil differences is in wide range (from 75 cm to 200 cm) and the thickness of humus horizon is 25-30 cm. In terms of mechanical composition, some soils are slightly sandy-clayey (physical clay in the arable layer 25-30%), but there are also heavy-sandy clay soils (physical clay in the arable layer 52-67%). The soil reaction is slightly acidic to neutral (pH H₂O 5.5-6.5). The field ratings for cereals are from 63 to 93, i.e. they are classified as "good" to "very good" lands.

The field ratings for corn and sunflower is in the range of 35-65 and depending on the soil difference, they are defined as "bad" to "moderately good" lands for these crops. The reduced rating for trench crops is due to the lower assessed rate for climate conditions in the region. As we noted, the moisture deficit during critical periods of crop development impacts on calculated ratings.

Field rating for fiber flax are in the range of 53-80 and classifies the lands as "average" to "very good" for growing the crop.

Conclusions

Ferric Lithosols - Profile 1, Dark Rankers – Profile 3 and Ferric rankers - Profile 4 and 7 belong to the category of "bad" lands for wheat (25-34 field rating), barley (25-45 field rating) and einkorn (30-38 field rating). For corn they are assessed as "unsuitable" lands (0-16 field rating). These soils receive the highest field rating for growing linseed 46-52, which means "medium-good lands".

With the largest production capacity for growing cereals are Leached cinnamon forest soils (Profiles 2, 5, 6), Typical cinnamon forest soils (Profile 8), Chernozems (Profile 9), Vertic (Resin-shaped) cinnamon forest soils (Profile 10). Field rating for cereals are from 63 to 93 and they are classified as "good" to "very good" lands.

The field ratings from the relative evaluation accurately show the suitability of individual soils for growing certain crops, because they include soil and climate conditions consistent with the requirements of plants. The results of the study can provide guidelines for appropriate zoning of crops, serve farmers, land tenants and other users.

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